

The Psalm Project

Discovering the Spiritual World through the Psalms

Psalm 140

Rev. Dr. Michael Harvey Koplitz

The Goal of this project:

This research project will examine the 150 psalms for the spiritual awareness each Psalm offers. Each Psalm will be examined by its language and the commentary of the Sages. The spiritual awareness analysis will be done in alignment with Ari's definition of the Tree of life, the Book of Creation, and the Zohar. Each verse of the Psalm will be rewritten using the intent of the language and spiritual commentary to convey its spiritual lesson.

The Main Resources:

The Zohar

The Book of Creation

Ari's writing on the Tree of Life and the Ten Sefirot

The Theological Wordbook of the Old Testament

Samson Hirsch's commentary on the Psalms

Tehillim – Psalms – A new translation with a commentary anthologized from the Talmudic and rabbinic sources

Accordance Bible Software

Psalm 140

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>Psa. 140:0 For the choir director. A Psalm of David.</p>	<p>Psa. 140:1 לְמִנְצַחַת מְזֻמֹּר לְדָוִד : 2</p>
<p>Psa. 140:1 "Rescue me, O LORD, from evil men; Preserve me from ^bviolent men ² Who ^adevise evil things in <i>their</i> hearts; They ^bcontinually stir up wars. ³ They ^asharpen their tongues as a serpent; ^bPoison of a viper is under their lips. ¹Selah.</p>	<p>חֲלֹצְנִי יְהוָה מֵאֲדָם רַע מֵאִישׁ חֲמָסִים תִּנְצֹרֵנִי : 3 אֲשֶׁר חָשְׁבוּ רָעוֹת בְּלֵב כָּל-יָוֵם יְגִוּרוּ מִלְחָמוֹת : 4 שָׁנְנוּ לְשׁוֹנָם כְּמוֹ-נִתְחַשׁ חֲמַת עַכְשָׁיוּב תַּחַת שִׁפְתֵימוֹ סֵלָה : 5 שָׁמְרֵנִי יְהוָה אֲמִידֵי רָשָׁע מֵאִישׁ חֲמָסִים תִּנְצֹרֵנִי אֲשֶׁר חָשְׁבוּ לְדַחֹת פְּעָמַי : 6 טִמְנוּ-גְּאִים אֶפְחָלִי וַחֲבָלִים פָּרְשׁוּ רֶשֶׁת לְיַד-מַעְגָּל מִקְנָשִׁים שָׁתוּ-לִי סֵלָה : 7 אֲמַרְתִּי לִיהוָה אֲנִי אֵתָהּ הֶאֱזִינָה יְהוָה קוֹל תַּחֲנוּנָי : 8 יְהוָה אֲדַנִּי עֹז יִשְׁעֵתִי סִכְתָּה לְרֹאשִׁי בַיּוֹם נִשְׁקָה : 9 אֶל-תַּתֵּן יְהוָה מֵאֲוֵי רָשָׁע זִמְמוֹ אֶל-תִּפְּק יַרְוֵמוֹ סֵלָה : 10 רֹאשׁ מִסְבֵּי עַמִּל שִׁפְתֵימוֹ יִכְסּוּמוֹ [יִכְסּוּמוֹ : 11 יְמִיטוּ [יְמִיטוּ] עַל־יָהֶם גִּחְלִים בָּאֵשׁ יִפְּלֹם בְּמַהֲמֹרוֹת בָּל-יִקְוֵמוֹ : 12 אִישׁ לְשׁוֹן בָּל-יִפּוֹן בְּאֶרֶץ אִישׁ-חָמָס רַע יִצְוֹדְנוּ לְמַדְחַפַּת : 13 יַדְעֵת [יַדְעֵתִי] כִּי-יַעֲשֶׂה יְהוָה בֵּין עַנְי מִשְׁפָּט</p>
<p>Psa. 140:4 "Keep me, O LORD, from the hands of the wicked; ^bPreserve me from violent men Who have ¹purposed to ²trip up my feet. ⁵ The proud have ^ahidden a trap for me, and cords; They have spread a ^bnet by the ¹wayside; They have set ^csnares for me. Selah.</p>	<p>מִלְחָמוֹת : 4 שָׁנְנוּ לְשׁוֹנָם כְּמוֹ-נִתְחַשׁ חֲמַת עַכְשָׁיוּב תַּחַת שִׁפְתֵימוֹ סֵלָה : 5 שָׁמְרֵנִי יְהוָה אֲמִידֵי רָשָׁע מֵאִישׁ חֲמָסִים תִּנְצֹרֵנִי אֲשֶׁר חָשְׁבוּ לְדַחֹת פְּעָמַי : 6 טִמְנוּ-גְּאִים אֶפְחָלִי וַחֲבָלִים פָּרְשׁוּ רֶשֶׁת לְיַד-מַעְגָּל מִקְנָשִׁים שָׁתוּ-לִי סֵלָה : 7 אֲמַרְתִּי לִיהוָה אֲנִי אֵתָהּ הֶאֱזִינָה יְהוָה קוֹל תַּחֲנוּנָי : 8 יְהוָה אֲדַנִּי עֹז יִשְׁעֵתִי סִכְתָּה לְרֹאשִׁי בַיּוֹם נִשְׁקָה : 9 אֶל-תַּתֵּן יְהוָה מֵאֲוֵי רָשָׁע זִמְמוֹ אֶל-תִּפְּק יַרְוֵמוֹ סֵלָה : 10 רֹאשׁ מִסְבֵּי עַמִּל שִׁפְתֵימוֹ יִכְסּוּמוֹ [יִכְסּוּמוֹ : 11 יְמִיטוּ [יְמִיטוּ] עַל־יָהֶם גִּחְלִים בָּאֵשׁ יִפְּלֹם בְּמַהֲמֹרוֹת בָּל-יִקְוֵמוֹ : 12 אִישׁ לְשׁוֹן בָּל-יִפּוֹן בְּאֶרֶץ אִישׁ-חָמָס רַע יִצְוֹדְנוּ לְמַדְחַפַּת : 13 יַדְעֵת [יַדְעֵתִי] כִּי-יַעֲשֶׂה יְהוָה בֵּין עַנְי מִשְׁפָּט</p>
<p>Psa. 140:6 I ^asaid to the LORD, "You are my God; ^bGive ear, O LORD, to the ^cvoice of my supplications. ⁷ "O ¹GOD the Lord, ^athe strength of my salvation, You have ^bcovered my head in the day of ²battle.</p>	<p>יְהוָה אֲנִי אֵתָהּ הֶאֱזִינָה יְהוָה קוֹל תַּחֲנוּנָי : 8 יְהוָה אֲדַנִּי עֹז יִשְׁעֵתִי סִכְתָּה לְרֹאשִׁי בַיּוֹם נִשְׁקָה : 9 אֶל-תַּתֵּן יְהוָה מֵאֲוֵי רָשָׁע זִמְמוֹ אֶל-תִּפְּק יַרְוֵמוֹ סֵלָה : 10 רֹאשׁ מִסְבֵּי עַמִּל שִׁפְתֵימוֹ יִכְסּוּמוֹ [יִכְסּוּמוֹ : 11 יְמִיטוּ [יְמִיטוּ] עַל־יָהֶם גִּחְלִים בָּאֵשׁ יִפְּלֹם בְּמַהֲמֹרוֹת בָּל-יִקְוֵמוֹ : 12 אִישׁ לְשׁוֹן בָּל-יִפּוֹן בְּאֶרֶץ אִישׁ-חָמָס רַע יִצְוֹדְנוּ לְמַדְחַפַּת : 13 יַדְעֵת [יַדְעֵתִי] כִּי-יַעֲשֶׂה יְהוָה בֵּין עַנְי מִשְׁפָּט</p>

⁸ “Do not grant, O LORD, the
^adesires of the wicked;
Do not promote ^bhis *evil* device,
that they not be exalted. Selah.

Psa. 140:9 “As for the head of those
who surround me,
May the ^amischief of their lips
cover them.

¹⁰ “May ^aburning coals fall upon
them;
May they be ^bcast into the fire,
Into ¹deep pits from which they
^ccannot rise.

¹¹ “May a ¹slanderer not be
established in the earth;
^aMay evil hunt the violent man
²speedily.”

Psa. 140:12 I know that the
LORD will ^amaintain the cause of the
afflicted

And ^bjustice for the poor.

¹³ Surely the ^arighteous will give
thanks to Your name;
The ^bupright will dwell in Your
presence.

אֲבִינִים : 14 אֵךְ צְדִיקִים יוֹדוּ
לְשִׁמְךָ יִשְׁבּוּ יִשְׂרָאֵל אֶת־פְּנֶיךָ :

References

Psalm 140:1

^aPs 17:13; 59:2; 71:4

^bPs 18:48; 86:14; 140:11

Psalm 140:2

^aPs 7:14; 36:4; 52:2; Prov 6:14; Is 59:4; Hos 7:15

^bPs 56:6

Psalm 140:3

¹*Selah* may mean: *Pause, Crescendo* or *Musical interlude*

^aPs 57:4; 64:3

^bPs 58:4; Rom 3:13; James 3:8

Psalm 140:4

¹Or *devised*

²Lit *push violently*

^aPs 71:4

^bPs 140:1

^cPs 36:11

Psalm 140:5

¹Lit *track*

^aJob 18:9; Ps 35:7; 141:9; 142:3

^bPs 31:4; 57:6; Lam 1:13

^cPs 141:9; Is 8:14; Amos 3:5

Psalm 140:6

^aPs 16:2; 31:14

^bPs 143:1

^cPs 116:1; 130:2

Psalm 140:7

¹Heb *YHWH*, usually rendered *LORD*

²Lit *weapons*

^aPs 28:8; 118:14

^bPs 144:10

Psalm 140:8

^aPs 112:10

^bEsth 9:25; Ps 10:2, 3

Psalm 140:9

^aPs 7:16; Prov 18:7

Psalm 140:10

¹Lit *watery*

^aPs 11:6

^bPs 21:9; Matt 3:10

^cPs 36:12

Psalm 140:11

¹Lit *man of tongue*

²Lit *thrust upon thrust*

^aPs 34:21

Psalm 140:12

^{a1} Kin 8:45, 49; Ps 9:4; 18:27; 82:3

^bPs 12:5; 35:10

Psalm 140:13

^aPs 97:12

^bPs 11:7; 16:11; 17:15

Targum

Psa. 140:1 For praise; a psalm composed by David. ² Deliver me, O LORD, from an evil son of man; protect me from the man of rapacity. ³ Who have plotted evil things in the heart; all the day they incite wars. ⁴ They teach with their tongue like a snake; the venom of the spider is under their lips forever. ⁵ Protect me, O LORD, from the hand of wicked men; protect me from the man of rapacity; who have plotted to attack my steps. ⁶ The proud have hidden a trap for me, and they spread out ropes as a net beside the path; they have placed snares for me always. ⁷ I said to the LORD, “You are my God.” Hear, O LORD, the sound of my petition. ⁸ God, the LORD, is the strength of my redemption; you have covered my head in the day of battle. ⁹ Do not grant, O LORD, the desires of Doeg the wicked; do not support his thoughts; let them be removed forever. ¹⁰ Ahithophel, head of the Sanhedrin of disciples — may the toil of the slander of their lips cover them. ¹¹ May coals from heaven come upon them; may he make them fall into the fire of Gehenna, in sparks that glow, lest they rise to eternal life. ¹² The man who speaks with deceitful tongue – they cannot dwell in the land of life; the angel of death will hunt down the men of evil rapacity, he will smite them in Gehenna. ¹³ Then it is manifest before me; for the LORD will work justice for the poor, justice for the needy. ¹⁴ Truly, the righteous will give thanks to your name; the upright will sit to pray before you.

Spiritual Awareness

Introduction

This Psalm reflects King David's dark and lonely feelings when Saul was chasing him. David knew that he was anointed to become Israel's king and that the LORD rejected Saul and his sons. David knew that the people chasing him were rejecting the LORD's decision to change Israel's leadership. The psalm also reflects that the Messiah would be a descendant of the House of David and divinely selected. The Messiah's task will be to gather the scattered Jews together and to fight the battle against Gog and Magog during the Messianic age.

Superscript

To the Sefirah Netzach who grants victory

Verse four

They have sharpened their tongue like a serpent; viper's venom is beneath their lips. Meditate on this verse.

Verse six

Who have proudly hidden snare and cords for me, who have spread a net for me by the wayside; they have a noose for me. Meditate on this verse.

Verse nine

Fulfill not, O LORD, the desires of the lawless, let me his aspiration grow so real that they could exalt themselves. Meditate on this verse.

Notes on this Psalm

The last verse is the key to the Psalm. Only the righteous will render homage to the Name of the LORD. The people who follow the Laws of the LORD as defined in the Torah will be called righteous and their reward will be eternity in the LORD's house, the Lower Waters of Heaven.

Appendix

Mystical Methodology to Prayer

All prayers result in spiritual energy which rises through the conduits that connect Sefirot realms. The "answer" to prayers is the transformation of spiritual energy from its original frequency to an appropriate frequency which will give the necessary results.

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Chambers of Aba and Ima of Briyah

Keter: prayers of thanksgiving come

MHK V1.1 6/23/14

